

ISic3109

I.Sicily inscription 3109

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Δάματρι καὶ [Κ]όραι

2. [---]ων καὶ ἃ γυναῖ αὐτοῦ Ἄρισ[--- κ]αὶ τὰ τέκνα ἀ[νέθηνκαν]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004. Line 1 is above the relief, Line 2 is below it.

Translation (en)

To Demeter and Kore/...and his wife Aris...and their children set this up (?)

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645454

PHI 316192

PHI 336511

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 59.1104
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 50.1009
undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1946-47.0264
Dubois, Laurent 2008. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile. Tome II.. Geneva. At 14
Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 1
Libertini, G 1937. Demetriaka. *Archaiologike Ephemeris*. 100: 715-726. At 721-726 fig.6
Libertini, G 1939. Relievo demetriaco da Catania. *Bollettino Storico Catanese*. 4: 124-128. At ph = Libertini (1981) 117-120
Manganaro, G. 1965. Ricerche di antichità e di epigrafia siceliote. *Archeologia Classica*. 17: 183-210. At 186
Löhr, C. 2000. Griechische Familienweihungen. Untersuchungen einer Repräsentationsform von ihren Anfängen bis zum Ende des 4. Jhs. v. Chr.. Rahden. At 59-60 no.54
Privitera, S. 2009. Due rilievi greci da Catania e il commercio di opere d'arte nella Sicilia tardo-repubblicana. *Annuario della Scuola Archeologica di Atene e delle Missioni Italiane in Oriente*. 87: 425-439.

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3109. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357152>